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Title: - Suicide Reporting Guidelines and Media Coverage: A Narrative Review

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Title:- A Review of Suicide Reporting Guidelines and Media Coverage

Abstract

Objective – This study examines national and international guidelines for suicide reporting in media and evaluates the extent of adherence and violations.

Methodology – A systematic review of literature published between 2020 and 2025 was conducted using PubMed, CORE, and Google Scholar. The review assessed compliance with WHO, PCI, SPIRIT, and three widely adopted international guidelines, applying the PRISMA 2020 framework to ensure rigorous screening and selection.

Results – Findings indicate partial compliance, with many reports prioritizing sensationalism over responsible reporting. Common violations include graphic descriptions of suicide methods, omission of helpline details, and inadequate framing of suicide as preventable. These lapses highlight the limited effectiveness of existing guidelines due to inconsistent application and weak enforcement mechanisms.

Conclusion – Strengthening regulations, standardizing media training, and fostering collaboration between media, policymakers, and mental health professionals are essential. Institutionalizing responsible reporting practices can enhance public awareness and contribute significantly to suicide prevention efforts in India.

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Highlights

- Finds partial compliance with sensationalism and missing helpline details.
- Recommends regulation, training, and collaboration for responsible reporting.

Keywords: Suicide reporting, suicide reporting guidelines, media and India.

1. Introduction

Suicide, with approximately 720,000 global deaths annually, remains a critical public health challenge (WHO, 2025). India significantly contributes to this burden, recording over 150,000 suicide deaths per year, thus necessitating targeted preventive interventions (NCRB, 2022). The impact of suicide extends beyond the individual, affecting families, communities, and broader social structures. Given the rise in suicide rates in many countries, including India and China—where nearly 40% of global suicides occur—there is a growing emphasis on prevention strategies, including media regulation (Raj et al., 2020). In light of this, broadcast media has gained prominence as a vital platform for implementing suicide prevention strategies.

Television and radio remain among the most influential channels of mass communication, capable of reaching diverse and extensive audiences rapidly—a reach that is underscored by Britannica’s definition of broadcasting as “the systematic dissemination of entertainment, information, educational programming, and other features for simultaneous reception by a scattered audience with appropriate receiving apparatus,” encompassing both audio formats like radio and audio-visual platforms like television (Camacho & Manvell, 2025).

Their widespread accessibility positions broadcast media uniquely to shape public perceptions and behaviors significantly, particularly concerning sensitive issues such as suicide—a role further evidenced by research showing that broadcast media reporting can profoundly influence public behavior and potentially trigger imitative suicidal acts, a phenomenon known as the Werther effect (Niederkröthaler et al., 2020). However, evidence also suggests that when broadcast media adopt a more responsible reporting style—emphasizing coping strategies and recovery narratives—they can mitigate the risk of contagion and foster a protective effect known as the Papageno effect (Niederkröthaler et al., 2020).

Given the impact of media portrayals, governments, and international organizations, including the World Health Organization (WHO), have established guidelines for responsible suicide reporting. These guidelines aim to reduce the risk of imitation suicides by discouraging sensationalized reporting, limiting detailed descriptions of suicide methods, and promoting awareness of mental health resources.

Despite the existence of these guidelines, adherence remains inconsistent. Several studies have documented widespread breaches in media reporting, including the sensationalization of suicide, explicit mention of methods, and failure to provide helpline information (Harshe et al., 2016; Menon et al., 2021; Niederkrotenthaler et al., 2020; Shamla et al., 2023). The rise of online media, where content is disseminated rapidly and often without editorial oversight, further complicates the enforcement of these guidelines (Raj et al., 2020). Additionally, celebrity suicides often trigger an overwhelming volume of media coverage, intensifying concerns about their influence on vulnerable populations (Banerjee, 2020; Jang et al., 2021).

Consequently, despite the potential for broadcast platforms to both harm and help public mental health, current evidence suggests that their reporting practices remain suboptimal in following established guidelines, thereby highlighting an urgent need for improved regulatory mechanisms and enhanced media training by mental health experts in this sector.

This review aims to explore the suicide reporting guidelines for broadcast media, assess the extent to which they are followed, and examine the broader implications of current reporting practices. By analyzing literature and case studies, this paper seeks to identify gaps in adherence and propose recommendations for improving it. In line with this objective, the study is guided by the following research questions:

- To what extent do broadcast media reports on suicide adhere to or violate the established guidelines?
- What patterns of non-compliance are most commonly observed in existing literature?

2. Methodology

2.1 Search Strategy-A systematic literature search was conducted using databases PubMed, Core, and Google Scholar to identify studies relevant to suicide reporting in broadcast media. The keywords utilized included “suicide reporting” “suicide reporting guidelines,” “media” and “India.” The initial search yielded a total of 173 articles, comprising 152 from Google Scholar, 17 from Core and 4 from PubMed respectively. Duplicate articles (n=13) were removed, and irrelevant articles (n=92) were excluded before screening, as they did not pertain to the research topic. In addition to peer-reviewed journal articles, gray literature was systematically incorporated into the review to capture a comprehensive understanding of suicide reporting guidelines across various countries. Grey literature sources included six guidelines published by national and international health organizations. These materials were identified through targeted searches on official websites and relevant organizational portals. The selection of organizational websites for suicide reporting guidelines was guided by

relevance, credibility, official status and regional applicability (guidelines from India were prioritized for contextual applicability, while international guidelines were selected for comparative purposes); ensuring that only authoritative and directly relevant guidelines were included in the review. The literature search was restricted to publications from the year 2020 to 2025. This timeframe was selected to ensure the inclusion of the most recent and relevant studies, particularly in light of evolving media practices, increased broadcast consumption and suicide reporting. Focusing on this period allows for a more current understanding of guideline adherence in contemporary broadcast media contexts.

2.2 Selection Criteria- Articles were screened based on their alignment with the study's objective, specifically focusing on analyzing adherence to suicide reporting guidelines. Articles from the past six years were prioritized; older pivotal studies were selectively included for contextual relevance. Systematic searches for gray literature from credible sources were included to ensure comprehensive insight into guideline practices globally and articles of the print media which held significant contextual value. Inclusion criteria emphasized empirical research on adherence to suicide reporting guidelines within broadcast and digital media, explicitly excluding print media. Only studies appearing within the first ten pages of Google Scholar were included due to diminishing relevance beyond these pages. Excluded studies included opinion pieces, non-peer-reviewed sources, articles without empirical data, and documents lacking comprehensive methodological frameworks.

2.3 Data Extraction- The screening process was carried out in a systematic and multi-stage manner by two independent researchers to ensure rigor and objectivity. Initially, 121 articles were shortlisted for full-text assessment. After the preliminary exclusion of duplicates 68 articles were left. From these, 26 articles were excluded due to the unavailability of full-text. Following this, the remaining 42 articles underwent a detailed eligibility assessment based on predefined inclusion criteria that focused on the relevance, quality, and alignment of each study with the research objective—specifically, the adherence to and effectiveness of suicide reporting guidelines in broadcast media. As a result of this process, 42 articles were found to meet all eligibility criteria and were included in the final analysis.

To maintain consistency and reduce bias, the two researchers independently screened each article at both the abstract and full-text levels. In cases where there were discrepancies or disagreements regarding the inclusion or exclusion of an article, a discussion was held between the three reviewers to reach consensus. This collaborative and transparent screening approach ensured that the final selection of articles was both reliable and aligned with the study's objectives, enhancing the overall validity of the findings.

The screening process followed the PRISMA 2020 (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) guidelines to ensure transparency and methodological rigor. A graphical flow of the search strategy is given in figure 1.

Figure 1- PRISMA Flow 2020.

3. Results

To understand the global landscape of suicide reporting guidelines and identify commonalities and divergences in their recommendations, a comparative analysis was conducted across selected national and international frameworks. The American Foundation for Suicide Prevention (AFSP), Samaritans, Mindframe, and WHO guidelines were selected as they are among the most widely followed across different continents, while the SPIRIT and PCI guidelines were included due to their regional relevance—SPIRIT offering guidance for India and Bangladesh, and PCI being developed specifically for the Indian context—making them essential for comparative analysis of adherence and violations in suicide reporting by the media. These guidelines emphasize ethical reporting practices aimed at preventing imitation suicides, by discouraging sensationalized portrayals, avoiding explicit method details, and promoting mental health awareness and preventive messages. Adherence to these guidelines is critically important, as responsible reporting can mitigate harmful contagion effects, support public mental health initiatives, and foster resilience among vulnerable populations.

3.1 Violation of the guidelines

Global Context- The global review of suicide reporting practices highlights widespread non-adherence to established media guidelines across countries. Common violations include omission of helpline information, use of sensational or speculative language, and explicit descriptions of suicide methods. While countries like Australia show gradual improvement, regions such as Indonesia and India continue to display high rates of harmful reporting practices, including method disclosure and identity revelation. Even in high-income nations like the UK and Canada, omissions of preventive resources and

overemphasis on emotional or graphic details persist. These patterns reveal that despite the availability of clear international guidelines, inconsistent implementation and lack of regulatory enforcement remain major barriers to responsible suicide reporting worldwide (table 1).

Table 1- Violations of suicide reporting guidelines across different countries.

Country	Violation of Guidelines
UK	69.4% omitted support resources; 30.1% included speculative triggers (Utterson et al., 2017).
Ireland	Lack of support service information, overemphasis on grief, failure to discuss broader issues (McTernan et al., 2018)
Bhutan	Inappropriate language, sensationalized headlines (Zangmo & Zangmo, 2019)
Canada	Detailed suicide method descriptions, linked to higher suicide rates (Sinyor et al., 2018)
Australia	Reduction in guideline breaches over time, but historical issues with explicit method reporting (Pirkis et al., 2009)
Indonesia	99.45% explicitly described methods; 68.07% did so in headlines (Nisa et al., 2020)
Taiwan	Front page reporting of suicide often with photograph (Chiang et al., 2016)
India	Sensationalism, identity disclosure, method details, lack of helpline info across multiple regions (Kar et al., 2022)
Nigeria	Reports often included personal details, methods, and lacked preventive information (Oyetunji et al., 2021)

Indian Context- Although this review focuses on broadcast media, it is important to note that the existing literature in the Indian context predominantly examines suicide reporting in print and online media. Despite television and radio being among the most widely consumed forms of media in India, there is a noticeable lack of empirical studies analyzing suicide coverage specifically in these formats. As a result, the studies presented in table 3 primarily reflect patterns, violations, and adherence in non-broadcast platforms. The analysis of suicide reporting in India reveals pervasive non-compliance with national and international guidelines across multiple media formats and regions. Sensationalism, detailed descriptions of suicide methods, disclosure of identities, and omission of helpline information are common violations. Reports on celebrity, farmer, and LGBTQI+ suicides often prioritize dramatization over sensitivity or context, while regional studies—from Tamil Nadu to Kerala—show widespread publication of explicit details and minimal inclusion of preventive messages. Online and

electronic media further amplify these issues through unregulated content dissemination. Overall, Indian media displays inconsistent adherence, reflecting a pressing need for stronger enforcement, journalist training, and integration of ethical, preventive frameworks in suicide reporting practices (table 2).

Table 2- Violations of suicide reporting guidelines in India

Aspect of Analysis	Violations of the Guidelines
Overall adherence to guidelines	Inconsistent (General Observation)
Celebrity suicide reporting	Media prioritizes sensationalism over ethical considerations (Menon et al., 2021)
Farmer suicide reporting	Sensationalism, inadequate contextual analysis, blaming individual factors instead of systemic issues (Rafi et al., 2017)
LGBTQI+ suicide reporting	Identity of deceased disclosed (55.6%), Method disclosed (54.3%). (Kar et al., 2023)
Online media reporting	Over 80% violated at least one guideline; common violations include sensationalist headlines, detailed suicide methods, absence of helpline information, lack of regulatory oversight (Raj et al., 2020); 61% non-compliance in an other study by Akkineni and Kakunje (2022).
Media reporting (Tamil Nadu)	95.9% reported specific suicide incidents, 43.3% detailed suicide method, only 2.5% provided helpline contacts. (Armstrong et al., 2018)
Media Reporting (Chandigarh)	60% portrayed suicide sensationally, and 98.5% revealed the identity of the decease; 92% failed to educate the public on suicide and mental illness (Sharma et al., 2021)
Media Reporting (Uttar Pradesh)	Method of suicide was mostly reported. Mental illness was attributed as a cause of suicide among 23.75% of the news reports. Less than 2% of the news reports referred to expert opinion (Kar et al., 2021).
Media Reporting (Odisha and Kerala)	60.6% of reports included summaries of suicide notes. Lacks positive reporting practices. (Kar et al., 2024)
Media Reporting (Kerala)	Reporting the name (93.9 %) and age (93.6 %) of the deceased, method of suicide (93.1 %), location of suicide (88.9 %), monocausal explanations (48.8 %), and including photograph of the deceased (37.7 %) were commonly noted. Poor adherence to international reporting guidelines, with very little focus on educating the public. (Menon et al., 2021)
Online suicide reporting (multiple languages)	Common inclusion of harmful details (methods, locations), omission of supportive resources information. (Shamla et al., 2023)
Suicide Reporting in Electronic and Print Media	98% of the analyzed reports did not mention any means to seek help; Nearly 100% of all the suicide reports were non-compliant in at least one of the parameters of guidelines. (Akkineni and Kakunje, 2022)

This concern is amplified by growing international and national evidence linking irresponsible media reporting to increases in suicide rates. Meta-analyses have shown that coverage of celebrity suicides is associated with a significant rise in suicide incidence—one study reported a 13% overall increase and a 30% rise in suicides by the same method when specific details are disclosed (Niederkröthaler et al., 2020). In India, following the suicide of actor Sushant Singh Rajput (SSR), 5.6% of reported suicides in the following month were directly linked to his death (Menon et al., 2021). Many of these had no prior history of mental illness or major stressors, suggesting that media coverage may have acted as a trigger. The method used by the celebrity was also disproportionately replicated, reinforcing evidence that detailed portrayals of suicide methods can influence vulnerable individuals (Pirkis & Blood, 2001).

Sensationalized reports in broadcast media can further normalize suicide as a coping mechanism, increasing the risk of imitation. In the aftermath of celebrity suicides, media outlets often intensify coverage with explicit descriptions of methods, quoted suicide notes, and oversimplified causal narratives (Harshe et al., 2016). These reports frequently omit protective elements such as helpline information or mental health resources. This pattern highlights the urgent need for media to follow responsible reporting guidelines to reduce harm, promote preventive messaging, and enhance public mental health literacy (Pirkis & Blood, 2001).

Although widespread violations of suicide reporting guidelines present significant risks, evidence indicates substantial benefits when guidelines are effectively followed. Following section discuss the studies that demonstrate responsible reporting can reduce suicide rates and enhance public mental health literacy.

3.2 Adherence to the guidelines

Above findings collectively underscore the dangers of guideline violations and the critical role media plays in either exacerbating or preventing suicide contagion. In contrast, a growing body of evidence demonstrates that responsible media reporting, aligned with established guidelines, can significantly improve the suicide report, reduce suicide risk and promote help-seeking behavior.

Evidence suggests that responsible broadcast reporting—emphasizing coping strategies and recovery—can reduce suicide risk. Studies in table 4 consistently show that adherence to media guidelines not only limits contagion but also promotes a protective effect, reinforcing the need for ongoing revision and enforcement of suicide reporting standards (Niederkröthaler et al., 2010; Pirkis and Blood, 2001) (Table 3).

Table 3- Changes in Suicide Reporting After Guideline Implementation.

Authors (Year)	Country	Positive Outcomes After Guidelines Implementation
Roskar et al. (2017)	Slovenia	54% of the evaluated reporting criteria showed statistically significant improvement, reduction in sensationalistic reporting and a decline in articles covering specific suicide cases.
Jang et al. (2021)	South Korea	Significant reduction in copycat suicides, marked by decreased daily suicide rates following celebrity suicides after guideline revisions and legislation.
Antebi et al. (2020)	Canada	High adherence to avoiding harmful reporting (>80% refrained from sensational language, monocausal explanations, glamorization). Lower adherence (17–22%) in providing protective content (helpline info, expert quotes, educational material).
Sinyor et al. (2024)	Canada	Significant reductions in harmful reporting practices alongside notable improvements in protective content across all measured indicators.
Chia et al. (2021)	Taiwan	High compliance (~90%) with WHO guidelines on 6 of 12 criteria, especially improved reporting by limiting details, avoiding simplistic explanations, and including helpline resources.
Ganesh et al. (2020)	Austria & Switzerland	Improved quality of suicide reporting practices and measurable reduction in imitation suicides due to consistent adherence to guidelines.
Shaw et al. (2025)	Guyana	Increased inclusion of helpline information and reduced stigmatizing language and explicit method details after WHO guideline introduction.

The identified widespread violations highlight critical gaps in guideline adherence. In the subsequent section, barriers contributing to these inconsistencies are explored.

4. Discussion

The findings of this review underscore significant gaps in the adherence of broadcast media to existing suicide reporting guidelines in India. Despite the existence of comprehensive recommendations developed by international and national health organizations, such as the World Health Organization (WHO, 2017), SPIRIT guidelines (SPIRIT, 2023), the Press Council of India (Raj et al., 2020), and the American Foundation for Suicide Prevention (Engelson et al., 2023), print media frequently deviate from established standards. These deviations primarily involve sensationalizing coverage through explicit descriptions of suicide methods, prominent and repetitive reporting, and inadequate incorporation of protective elements such as helpline numbers and mental health resources.

A key finding was the prevalent practice of detailing methods of suicide, particularly following high-profile celebrity cases. Studies such as those by Niederkrotenthaler et al. (2020) and Menon et al. (2021) consistently indicate that such graphic reporting significantly contributes to suicide contagion. The

implications of these breaches are profound, given broadcast media's broad reach and powerful visual and auditory capabilities, which heighten the emotional impact of content, potentially normalizing suicide as a viable coping mechanism among vulnerable viewers.

Adherence to suicide reporting guidelines is impeded by significant barriers including inadequate journalist training, limited mental health literacy, and organizational pressures towards sensationalism. Studies highlight shifts towards sensationalist reporting following celebrity suicides, emphasizing detailed methods and neglecting protective information, exacerbating suicide contagion risks (Harshe et al., 2016; Utterson et al., 2017; Zangmo & Zangmo, 2019; McTernan et al., 2018). Addressing these barriers necessitates systemic interventions such as structured training programs, reforms in newsroom practices, and sustained collaboration between media and mental health professionals to foster responsible reporting.

Research also demonstrates that responsible media reporting significantly reduces suicide risks, particularly by highlighting coping mechanisms, recovery narratives, and preventive resources (Niederkrotenthaler et al., 2010). Empirical evidence from countries such as South Korea (Jang et al., 2021), Canada (Antebi et al., 2020; Sinyor et al., 2024), Taiwan (Chia et al., 2021), Guyana (Shaw et al., 2025), and Slovenia (Roškar et al., 2017) underscores substantial improvements in reporting quality, with reduced sensationalism, diminished explicit method details, and enhanced inclusion of helpline information following guideline implementation. This underscores the importance of balanced, informed, and sensitive reporting in suicide prevention efforts.

Additionally, enforcement mechanisms are generally advisory rather than mandatory, reducing the efficacy of guidelines. Engelson et al. (2023) highlighted that adherence to reporting guidelines, particularly concerning celebrity suicides, remains voluntary in many jurisdictions, contributing to inconsistent compliance and perpetuating harmful reporting practices. This voluntary nature of adherence often leads broadcasters to prioritize sensational elements intended to boost ratings, overshadowing ethical considerations and public health responsibilities.

An essential factor often overlooked in suicide reporting is the active collaboration between media professionals and mental health experts. Such partnerships can significantly enhance the quality and sensitivity of suicide coverage in broadcast media. Mental health professionals with their specialized knowledge and expertise, can guide journalists on the nuances of suicide reporting, helping them avoid common pitfalls such as oversimplification, sensationalism, and explicit method descriptions (Engelson et al., 2023). Integrating mental health experts into newsroom practices, either through regular training workshops, editorial consultations, or direct involvement in crafting narratives around suicide-related news, could substantially improve adherence to guidelines and contribute positively towards public mental health outcomes. Moreover, ongoing collaboration helps media personnel manage their own

emotional and psychological responses to reporting on traumatic events, fostering a supportive environment that ultimately benefits both professionals and the broader community (SPIRIT, 2023).

The proliferation and amplification of broadcast content through digital and social media platforms represent another layer of complexity. Engelson et al. (2023) illustrated that social media significantly amplifies broadcast narratives, often disseminating content rapidly and widely without adherence to guidelines, exacerbating potential harm. This compounds the Werther phenomenon by extending the reach of harmful reporting practices beyond original broadcast audiences, highlighting the urgent need for integrated media strategies that span both traditional and digital platforms.

The ethical responsibilities of broadcast media are profound, necessitating a careful balance between the freedom of expression and the obligation to safeguard public health. The moral imperative for media organizations to adopt responsible reporting practices is clear. Ensuring such responsibility requires intersectoral collaboration involving media professionals, mental health experts, policymakers, and civil society. Such collaborations can facilitate the development and dissemination of tailored broadcast-specific guidelines, emphasizing ethical standards and public health priorities.

Recommendations

This review underscores the necessity of developing robust, enforceable broadcast-specific guidelines. Institutionalizing regular training sessions for broadcast journalists and editors, incorporating mental health literacy, ethical considerations, and the implications of irresponsible reporting, is essential.

Training modules on responsible suicide reporting should be integrated into journalism school curricula to equip future media professionals with the knowledge and sensitivity required for ethical reporting on mental health and suicide-related issues. Regular collaboration between media houses and mental health experts is essential to ensure that reporting remains aligned with current best practices, allowing for continuous updates to guidelines and fostering informed, compassionate coverage. Moreover, integrating mental health professionals within newsroom processes as consultants or advisors during sensitive reporting can check adherence to ethical standards and enhance the quality of content.

The establishment of oversight mechanisms is critical to monitor and confirm adherence to suicide reporting guidelines. Regulatory bodies or independent media oversight organizations could be mandated to regularly review and assess reporting practices, issue corrective advisories, and provide accountability measures for repeated violations. Implementing legal frameworks or regulatory standards may further incentivize compliance, encouraging media organizations to adopt responsible practices proactively.

In light of the limited empirical evidence on suicide reporting within Indian broadcast media, there is a clear need to expand research efforts in this area. Given the widespread consumption and emotional resonance of television and radio, understanding how these platforms portray suicide is essential for assessing their impact on public behavior and mental health outcomes. Future research should aim to systematically examine reporting patterns, guideline adherence, and potential contagion effects in broadcast formats. Such evidence would provide a critical foundation for the development of context-specific policies, regulatory frameworks, and training programs that address the unique challenges of suicide reporting in the Indian broadcast media landscape.

Limitations

Despite the comprehensive insights gained through this review, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the study relied extensively on secondary data from previously published research and guidelines, which may inherently limit the scope of analysis, particularly in contexts where academic studies are sparse. Second, the lack of media diversity in the reviewed literature. The majority of the included articles primarily focused on suicide reporting in print and online media, while no studies were found that examined adherence to suicide reporting guidelines in broadcast content.

Additionally, artificial intelligence (AI) tools were used in certain sections of this manuscript to enhance academic clarity and language precision, which may have influenced phrasing but not the interpretation of findings.

Conclusion

This review highlights the critical need for media to rigorously adhere to suicide reporting guidelines, emphasizing responsible, ethical, and informed coverage as a public health priority. Addressing the identified gaps through targeted recommendations—such as specialized training, guideline enforcement mechanisms, and intersectoral collaborations—can significantly enhance the positive impact of broadcast media in suicide prevention efforts, ultimately safeguarding vulnerable populations and promoting broader mental health literacy and awareness through ethical and responsible practices.

Conflict of Interest

The author declares no competing interests.

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